

An identity of Afro-American Women in a Movie adapted from the Novel of Alice Walker's 'The Color Purple'

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Abstract

To bring out the identity of Afro-American Women in a Movie adapted from the Novel of Alice Walker's 'The Color Purple'. At certain points during that period of time, Alice Walker as a Black woman, she herself has been exposed to many hard times she has survived periods of hardship and raised her voice over the difficulties of Black women in African- American society. She has special place in African American literature. Her novels mainly focus on the lives of Black female characters and their hardships. Walker, in her novels, explores the problems of these women who struggle to achieve independent identities beyond their complications to keep their creativity and strength alive. This study appearance profound at the causes of women's sufferings and a crisis of personal identity and the solution for their difficulties and the relationships among the women. It discusses whether the female distress is because of confined and wretchedness misery, whether it comes from characters' flaws, they are suffered to be deprived and tend to hesitate, whether men and society are the major cause of their problems. Although female characters are the central point of the segment, the male characters are also investigated to learn about their relationships with women and to learn if they face any crisis or suffering. It explicit the point that an issue can reach the audience, heedless of barriers and that literature could change the psyche of the readers.

“I think Africans are very much like white people back home, in that they think they are the center of the universe and that everything that is done is done for them.” - Alice Walker

The article argues that the preservation of one's native culture is more important than assimilation and acculturation. It also discusses the African American women's life and their condition as portrayed by Alice Walker in her debut novel *The color purple*. Alice walker talks about her African identity and expresses her ideas through her writing. Life writing of a person is in a way a work of literature. Alice described this as being a very difficult time in her life. Still reeling from the grief over death of her father and her divorce, Alice turned to writing to prolong her through the pain. She began work on a third work of poetry, *Good Night willie Lee, I'll see you in the Morning*. After her poems were sent to her publisher, Alice began the genesis of what would be her third novel and most celebrated novel.

Since she has received much critical acclaim for her novel, Meridian the prestigious Guggenheim Foundation awarded her a grant in 1978. The grant was enough to live off and help her to keep her focus solely on her writing.

Women all over the world face many challenges and struggles that make their lives despondent and intolerable. While some women stand up for themselves and become content with them, others feel ashamed of whom they are. In the color purple by Alice Walker, the protagonist, Celie, gets described by her husband, Albert, her stepfather, Alphonso, and her husband's ex-girlfriend, Shug, as ugly. The oppression that Celie is subjected to results in a deficient in of purpose and direction in her life. The absence of decisive activity generates a vacancy in women's lives and has been discussed by many critics like Betty Friedan who had commented that without a purpose woman loses the sense of who they are as it is the purpose which gives the human pattern to one's life. Gender oppression is also a main factor operating in the oppressive paternal ideology in which a father's control of the family's private resources effectively gives him license to violate his women. It reveals the family's weak internal structures in African – American families where a girl child is not safe even in her own family. The word “domestic” usually implies the sense of protection, comfort and the place where one can feel one's own identity.

A common form of film adaptation is the use of a novel as the basis of a feature film, but film adaptation includes the use of non-fiction including journalism, autobiography, comic book, scripture, plays, and even other films. From the earliest days of cinema, adaptation has been nearly as common as the development of original screenplays. In some cases, however, film adaptations will also interpose scenes or formulate characters. When source novels have elucidation or digressions from the author's own voice, a film adaptation may create a commenting, chorus-like character to endow with what could not be filmed otherwise. Film makers would rely upon voice over for a main character's thoughts, but while some films may self-consciously invoke the older epoch of film by the use of voice over, such devices have been used a lesser amount of occasion.

Literary texts provide a vein of raw material which is already tested. Film makers are not known for offering such blunt commercial reasons for making meticulous adaptations, and the writing of the adaptation is itself is a creative task, writers of adaptations rarely announce innovative or bold approaches to their subject matter, tending instead toward concern of not astonishment for their ‘literary source’

The novel *The color Purple* was basically written for the white audience so as to inform the world about the sufferings of the blacks under their supremacy. The movie was directed in a way so that it could gratify and entertain the whites. It portrayed a dark image of the black which bring about the black critics especially the women critics. The fact that Celie in moments of extreme physical pain transforms herself into a tree is a telling example of “a black woman's proximity to the passive suffering and agony of nature”. (Badode 38). In the same way when people compliment her on how good she is to Mr. ----'s children, she says, “I be good to them. But I don't feel anything for them. Patting Harpo back not even like patting a dog. It's more like patting a piece of wood. Not a living tree, but a table, a chifferobe” (31). Such comparisons with nature suggest dehumanization, retreat from feeling, a conscious aloofness of individual from feeling, a conscious aloofness of individual from surroundings as a result of lack of self-worth and self-esteem which is testified by Celie's cancellation of the word(s) “I am” on the very first page of the novel.

In the year 1982, Alice Walker wrote a highly acclaimed novel which won her the American Book Award and a Pulitzer Prize for fiction: *The Color Purple*. It was one of the first recognized books dealing with black women living in poor circumstances and being abused by men. As *The Color Purple* had reached a large audience causing both debate and positive recognition Hollywood had the idea of turning the *Color Purple* into a feature film. They approached Alice Walker who

at first didn't agree with the thought of someone else agreed and signed a contract. The reason for her giving in was the trust in Quincy Jones. Another explanation for setting on the big screen was the fact that many black people are illiterate and therefore is not capable of reading her story. The indenture included that Alice Walker was bound to the venture by working with the filmmakers at the set and having to decide about the screenplay. Another claim Alice Walker made was "[...] the stipulation that half the people involved in the production, apart from the predominantly black cast, would be blacks, women and/or people of the Third world." (Featherson, 183).

The novel *The Color Purple*, by Alice Walker, and the movie *The Color Purple* directed by Steve Spielberg, are stories about love and the survival between two sisters. The obstacles that the sisters have to face are very life risking. Although the novel and the movie have more similarities than differences, they still explain the major theme of womanhood. The novel and the movie have many of the same themes, obstacles, and resolutions. A similarity is Celie's stepfather raped her. After she was raped she had two children named Adam and Olivia, they were the given to Samuel and Corrine who were not able to have children. Another similarity is that Celie is afraid of men. "I don't even look at men. That's the truth. I look at woman, tho, cause I'm not scared of them." Celie said in her letter to God. (Walker, 6)

An anguish of a woman has very much portrays in the story. For example, the character Celie suffers for so long, she determines to stand up for herself, face the obstacles and seek a new path that drives her to the road of happiness. Celie leaves her husband after she learns that her husband hides her sister's letters from her. Celie's personality changes immensely and she feels very angry at her husband because he made her lose contact with the only person who loved her, it's none other than her sister Nettie. For instance, Celie starts fighting for herself; when she informs her husband that she will be leaving him, he cuts her with his eye and shoots her with his words, he says, "You black, you pore, you ugly, you a woman. Goddam, he say, you nothing at all," (Walker 209). Additionally, Celie powerfully expresses her feelings by sayings, "I'm pore, I'm black, I may be ugly and can't cook, a voice say to everything listening. But I'm here." (Walker 210). She goes on with standing up for herself in her husband's house until she leaves it which helps her to gain confidence and become content with herself. Celie's refusal to accept her husband's viciousness, and her fortitude to speak up for herself would sooner or later help her to gain confidence, be at ease with herself and have a better life.

Although the novel and the movie have more similarities than it has differences, it still explains the major theme of womanhood. All in all, both the film and the novel *The Color Purple* are not only entertaining, but very interesting because it taught the reader about how life was lived when there was discrimination of blacks and woman. Spielberg followed Walker's plot, but had to alter a few scenes to make them appropriate for television. This story was very pleasurable, but may cause (you) all to cry at times. The viewer or the reader is sure to love this uplifting story and is sure to get addicted to it. The narrative strategies construct a good cry in narrative fiction and *The Color Purple* is a fine example of that. It presents the crude reality of African American's life through the language and projection.

Henceforth, the major reason to choose this book is to show how things can be portrayed differently when novels are made into movies. The novel was purposefully written for non-Africans to give a pictorial representation of the African Americans under the white oppression. The white director directs the movie. Therefore, the things which Alice intended to say the white audience has been indistinct according to their ease. Though these things are very unambiguously portrayed in the movie a closer analysis reveals them. The novel by Alice Walker is that being content with ourselves can make our life cheerful, joyful and may as well allow us to achieve the goals and to be successful in our life. Without a doubt, understanding once of the themes can make the novel a crystal clear and very appealing.

The patriarchal construction of the difference between Masculinity and femininity is the political difference between freedom and subjection. (Pateman, 207)

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